

Qualitative Study on Philosophical Issues in Teaching and Learning Outcomes of Secondary School Students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Some philosophical schools (on teaching approaches) and proffered teaching approaches methods have been captured in this study to further examine and proffer effective teaching methods for teachers. The study adopted a quantitative research design which involve a historical method analysis and prescription. Thus, the study looked at philosophical schools of thought on teaching approaches like essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionism, conservatism and humanism, and their views on teaching approaches/ methods. The study concludes that teaching should be student-centered, teacher-centered and society-centered among others. The researchers recommended among others that different approaches or methods should be applied in the teaching and learning process, as this will benefit each student at their different levels of ability and capability.

Keywords: Philosophical issues, Teaching strategies, Secondary schools, Education

Introduction

Teaching is to assist the pupil to learn and acquire the desired knowledge, skills and also desirable ways of living in the society (Dewey, 2018). It is a process in which learners, teacher, curriculum and other variables are organized in a systematic and psychological way to attain some predetermined goals (Dewey, 2018). The chief task of education is, above all, to shape man or to guide the evolving dynamism through which man forms himself as a man. Teaching by philosophers refers to the pedagogical approaches and methods employed by philosophers or teachers to convey philosophical ideas, concepts, and critical thinking skills to students (Plato, 380 BCE). Philosophers often use innovative and engaging teaching methods to encourage critical thinking, dialogue, and reflection. Some common approaches include; Socratic method which involves encouraging questioning and dialogue to explore ideas and concepts (Paul et al., 2006). Critical thinking exercises; using logical thinking skills, exploring complex ideas through hypothetical scenarios and imaginative exercises (Paul et al, 2006). Philosophical debates; encouraging students to engage in respectful debates and discussions on philosophical topics (Paul et al., 2006). Reflective journaling; encouraging students to reflect on their thoughts, ideas and beliefs through writing (Paul et al., 2006). Case study; analyzing real-life scenarios and applying philosophical concepts to practice issues and conceptual analysis, breaking down complex concepts into their constituent parts to understand their meaning and implications.

An effective teacher at secondary school level of education in Cross River State.

The skills needed for effective teaching involves more than just expertise in an academic field. There should be strong communication skills; the teacher must be able to interact with people and help them understand a new way of looking at the world, this is not an easy job. Although there are many different ways to teach effectively, good instructors have several qualities in common; they are prepared, set clear and fair expectations, have a positive attitude, are patient with students and assess their teaching on a regular basis. They have a deep understanding of the subject matter being taught, and have the ability to create and maintain a well-organized and respectful classroom environment. They are able to adjust their teaching strategies to fit both the students and the materials, recognizing that different students learn in different ways. They have the ability to think critically and solve problems, the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. They are flexible, which means they adopt to changing circumstances and are flexible in teaching approaches. These qualities will

be respected in the attitudes of the students. Keep the students engaged with a positive attitude. Teaching is most effective when students are motivated by the desire to learn, rather than grades or degree requirements. The student should be thought of as a team mate, not adversary. Learning and teaching are challenging, but that does not mean that the teacher cannot have fun in the classroom. Stay focused, but not afraid to be creative and innovative. The teacher should allow himself to be enthusiastic and find ways to let students see what is interesting about their subject. Effective teachers can explain complex ideas in simple ways. The teacher should keep the students thinking; unless they are using the concepts the teacher is teaching, most students will remember only a small fraction of what they are taught. The teacher should consider using the classroom time for activities other than traditional lectures, discussions or question and answer sessions, problem solving exercises in small groups can take not more than a few minutes, yet students should be allowed to engage with the material being covered.

Each individual has an attitude towards life, children, politics, learning and previous personal experiences that inform and shape their set of beliefs or personal philosophy, informs how one lives, works and interact with others. What one believes is directly reflected in both one's teachings and learning process. This is why it is important that subject that teach tolerance and respect for one another be not just included in the curriculum but be properly taught (Onah et al., 2021). It is important to understand how philosophy and education are interrelated. In order to become the most effective teacher one can be, one must understand one's own beliefs, while at the same time empathizing with others. The major philosophies of education can be broken down into three main types; teacher centered philosophies, student centered philosophies, and society- centered philosophies. These include essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionisms, existentialism, behaviorism, constructivism, conservatism and humanism.

Conceptual clarification on teaching strategies at secondary school level of education in Cross River State.

1. **Philosophical issues:** This refers to fundamental problems, questions, or concerns that arise from the study of philosophy, encompassing various branches such as metaphysics, epistemology, ethics, logic and aesthetics (CDP, 2015). These issues often involve abstracts, fundamental questions, conceptual ambiguities, theoretical debates and methodological concerns like; who is an effective teacher? And what are the most effective and appropriate teaching methods?
2. **Teaching strategies:** This refers to the process of facilitating learning, guiding and monitoring students to acquire knowledge, skills, values and attitudes (CDP, 2015). It involves transmission of knowledge, facilitating learning, guiding, monitoring, role modeling, building relationship encouraging critical thinking and creating learning experience amongst others.
3. **Secondary schools:** the philosophical meaning of secondary school can be explore from various perspectives, for the purpose of this study, it is a platform for transmitting knowledge from teacher to student. It encourages critical thinking development as students learn to analysis, evaluate, and synthesize information (Steffe, 2018).
4. **Learning outcomes:** This can be understood through various lenses, philosophically; Pragmatism: Learning outcomes are the practical applications of knowledge, emphasizing utility and effectiveness (Taylor, 2019). Constructivism: Learning outcomes are the constructed meanings and understandings individuals create through experience and social interaction (Taylor, 2019). Essentialism: Learning outcomes are the essential knowledge, skills, and values that constitute a well- educated person (Baehr, 2019). Existentialism: Learning outcomes are the personal, subjective, and authentic experiences that foster individual growth and self-awareness. For the purpose of this study, learning outcomes are specific, measurable and achievable statements that describe what students will know, understand and are able to do as a result of a learning experience (Heyman, 2020).

Theoretical framework

Essentialism and perennialism are two types of teacher-centered philosophies of education. Essentialism is currently the leading style of public education in the United States (Ornstein et al., 2018). It is the teaching of basic skills that have been proven over time to be needed in society. Perennialism focuses on the teaching of great works. There are three types of student-centered philosophies of education; progressivism focuses on developing the students' moral compass and humanism is about fostering each student to his or her fullest potential. Constructivism focuses on using education to shape a students' world view (Steffe, 2018).

There are two types of socially- centered philosophies of education; progressivism focuses on developing the students' moral compass. Humanism is about fostering each student to his or her fullest potential. Constructivism focuses on using education to shape a student's world view. There are two types of socially- centered philosophies of education; reconstructionism is the perspective that education is the means to solve social problems (Taylor, 2019). Behaviorism focuses on cultivating behaviours that are beneficial to society. The constructivist teaching is based on constructivist learning theory.

Constructivist teaching is based on the belief that learning occurs as learners are actively involved in a process of meaning and knowledge construction as opposed to passively receiving information (Taylor, 2019). Learners are the makers of meaning and knowledge. One of the goals of using constructivist teaching is that students learn how to learn by giving them the training to take initiative for their own learning experiences. The characteristics of a constructivist classroom are as follows; the learners are actively involved, the environment is democratic, the activities are interactive and student centered, and the teacher facilitates a process of learning in which students are encouraged to be responsible and autonomous. Furthermore, in the constructivist classroom, students work primarily in groups and learning and knowledge are interactive and dynamic (Rowe, 2011).

There is a great focus and emphasis on social and communication skills, as well as collaboration and exchange of ideas. This is contrary to the traditional classroom in which students work primarily alone, learning is achieved through repetition, and the subjects are strictly adhered to and are guided by a textbook. Some activities encouraged in constructivist classrooms are;

Experimentation: Students individually perform an experiment and then come together as a class to discuss the results (Rowe, 2011). **Research projects:** Students research a topic and can present their findings to the class, **Field trips:** This allows students to put the concepts and ideas discussed in class in a real-world context. Field trips would often be followed by class discussions films. These provide visual context and thus bring another sense into the learning experience (Lipman, 2015). **Class discussions:** This technique is used in all of the methods described above. It is one of the most important distinctions of constructivist teaching methods (Bell, 2017). **Campus wikis:** These provide learners with a platform for curative helpful learning resources (Bell, 2017).

Constructivist approaches can also be used in online learning. For example, tools such as discussion forums, wikis and blogs can enable learners to actively construct knowledge. In the constructivist classroom, the teacher's role is to prompt and facilitate discussion. Thus, the teachers main focus should be on guiding students by asking questions that will lead them to develop their own conclusion on the subject. Good teachers join self, subject, and students in the fabric of life because they teach from an integral and undivided self, they manifest in their own lives and evoke in their students, a capacity for connectedness. Learning is driven by the problem to be solved, students learn context and theory in order to solve the problem. This is different from traditional objectivist teaching where the theory would be presented first and problems would be used afterwards to practice theory (Rowe, 2011). In constructivist teaching the process of gaining knowledge is viewed as being just as important as the product. Thus, assessment is based not only on tests but also on observation of the students, the students' work and the students' point of view (Onah et al., 2021). One possible deferent for this teaching method is that, due to the emphasis on group work, the ideas of the more active students may dominate the group's conclusion. On the other hand, educational essentialism is an educational philosophy whose adherents believe that children should learn the traditional basic subjects thoroughly (Heyman, 2020).

In this philosophical school of thought, the aim is to instill students with the 'essentials' of academic knowledge, enacting a back to fundamental approach. Essentialism ensures that the accumulated wisdom of our civilization as taught in the traditional academic disciplines is passed on from teacher to student. Such disciplines might include reading, writing, literature, foreign languages, history, mathematics, science, art and music (Rowe, 2011). This traditional approach is meant to train the mind, promote reasoning, and ensure a common culture. Essentialism is a relatively conservative stance to education that strives to teach students the knowledge of a society, and civilization through a core curriculum (Heyman, 2020). This core curriculum involves such areas that include the study of the surrounding environment, basic natural laws, and the disciplines that encourage a happier, more educated living (Baehr, 2019). Other non-traditional areas are also integrated as well in moderation to balance the education. Essentialists goals are to instill students with the 'essentials' of academic knowledge, patriotism and character development through traditional (or back to basics) approaches. This is to promote reasoning, train the mind, and ensure a common culture for all citizens.

Essentialism as a teacher-centered philosophy

The role of the teacher as a leader of the classroom is a very important tenet of educational essentialism (Rowe, 2015). The teacher is the center of the classroom, so they should be rigid and disciplinary. Establishing order in the classroom is crucial for students learning, effective teaching cannot take place in a loud and disorganized environment. It is the teachers' responsibility to keep order in the classroom. The teacher must interpret essentials of the learning process, take the leadership position and set the tone of the classroom. These needs require an educator who is academically well-qualified with an appreciation for learning and development. The teacher must control the students with distributions of rewards and penalties.

Although it is difficult to maintain a pure and strict essentialist only- curriculum, these schools have the central aim of establishing a common knowledge base for all citizens (Rowe, 2015). To do so, they follow a nationwide, content-specific,

and teacher centered curriculum. The core knowledge curriculum also allows for local variance above and beyond the core curriculum. Central curricular aims are academic excellence and the learning of knowledge, and teachers who are masters of their knowledge areas serve this aim. Because Essentialism is largely teacher centered, the role of the student is often called into question. Presumably, in an essentialist classroom, the teacher is the one designing the curriculum for the students based upon the core disciplines. Moreover, he or she is enacting the curriculum and setting the standards which the students must meet. The teachers' evaluative role may undermine students' interest in study. As a result, the students begin to take on more of a passive role in their education as they are forced to meet and learn such standards and information.

Furthermore, Educational Perennialism is a normative educational philosophy. Perennialists believe that one should teach the things that are of everlasting pertinence to all people everywhere, and that the emphasis should be on principles, not facts (Taylor, 2019). Since people are human, one should teach first about human, rather than machines or techniques and about liberal, rather than vocational topics. Although perennialism may appear similar to essentialism, perennialism focuses first on personal development, while essentialism focuses first on essential skills. Essentialist curricula thus tend to be much more vocational and fact-based, and far less liberal and principle-based. Both philosophies are typically considered to be teacher-centered, as opposed to student-centered philosophies of education such as progressivism. However, since the teacher associated with perennialism are in a sense the authors of the Western masterpieces themselves, these teachers may be open to student criticism through the associated Socratic method, which, if carried out as true dialogue, involves a balance between teacher activity and student activity with the teacher promoting discussion.

Perennialists believe that reading is to be supplemented with mutual investigations (between the teacher and the student) and minimally- directed discussions through the Socratic method in order to develop a historically-oriented understanding of concepts (Taylor, 2019). They argue that accurate, independent reasoning distinguishes the developed or educated mind and they thus stress the development of this faculty. A skilled teacher would keep discussions on topic and correct errors in reasoning, but it would be the class, not the teacher, who would reach the conclusions while not directing or leading the class to a conclusion, the teacher may work to accurately formulate problems within the scope of the texts being studied.

Perennialists freely acknowledge that any particular selection of great books will disagree on many topics, however, they see this as an advantage, rather than a detriment (Lipman, 2015). They believe that the student must learn to recognize such disagreements which often reflect current debates. The student becomes responsible for thinking about the disagreements and reaching a reasoned, defensible conclusion. This is a major goal of the Socratic discussions. They do not advocate teaching a settled scholarly interpretation of the books, which would cheat the student of the opportunity to learn rational criticism and to know his own mind.

One of the problems of perennialism is the issue of enlightenment; it is all about an individual attainment and not about the greater good of the human and natural communities that make our individual lives possible. Enlightenment offers nothing towards a sustainable future for humans and planet earth beyond the freedom from suffering that individual humans allegedly achieve through their own attainment of enlightenment. Spirituality is often considered to be in no small part, about growing beyond our selfish and self-centered tendencies, enlightenment appears to be the ultimate expression of self-centeredness. Another and perhaps the most troubling problem with enlightenment is that nobody can seem to agree on what it actually is. If enlightenment is truly the purpose and destiny of all human life, then those who attain enlightenment should describe it the same way, or at least in similar ways.

Progressivism – Philosophy of teaching/ education

Progressivists believe that education should focus on the whole child rather than on the content or the teacher (Baehr, 2019). This educational philosophy stresses that students should test ideas by active experimentation. Learning is rooted in the question of learners that arise through experiencing the world. It is active not passive. The learner is a problem solver and thinker who make meaning through his or her individual experience in the physical and cultural context. Effective teachers provide experiences that students can learn by doing. Curriculum content is derived from students' interest and questions. The scientific method is used by progressivists educators so that students can study matter and events systematically and first hand. The emphasis is on process- how one comes to know. John Dewey was its foremost proponent. One of his tenets was that school should improve the way of life of our citizens through experiencing freedom and democracy in schools. Shared decision making, planning of teachers with students, student-selected topics are all aspects. Books are tools, rather than authority.

Social Reconstructionism

Is a philosophy that emphasizes the addressing of social question and a quest to create a better society and worldwide democracy (Onah et al., 2021). Reconstructionist educators focus on a curriculum that highlights social reform as the aim of education. Theodore Brameld was the founder of social reconstructionism, in reaction against the realities of World War II. He

recognized the potential for either human annihilation through technology and human cruelty or the capacity to create a beneficent society using technology and human compassion. George Counts recognized that education was the means of preparing people for creating this new social order.

Critical theorists like social reconstructionist, believe that systems must be changed to overcome oppression and improve human conditions. In their view human must learn to resist oppression and not become its victims, nor oppress others. To do so requires dialogue and critical consciousness, the development of awareness to overcome domination and oppression. Rather than ‘teaching as banking’ in which the educator deposits information into students’ heads. They see teaching and learning as a process of inquiry in which the child must invent and reinvent the world. For social reconstructionist and critical theorists, curriculum focuses on student experience and taking social action on real problems, such as violence, hunger, international terrorism, inflation, and inequality. Strategies for dealing with controversial issues (particularly in social studies and literature), inquiry, dialogue, and multiple perspectives are the focus. Community-based learning and bring the world into the classroom are also strategies.

Existentialism

Is a philosophy that emphasizes individual existence, freedom and choice (Dewey, 2018). It is the view that humans define their own meaning in life, and try to make rational decisions despite existing in an irrational universe. It focuses on the question of human existence and the feeling that there is no purpose or explanation at core of existence. It holds that, as there is no God or any other transcendent force, the only way to counter this nothingness (and hence to find meaning in life) is by embracing existence. Thus, existentialism believes that individuals are entirely free and must take personal responsibility for themselves (although with this responsibility comes a profound anguish or dread). It therefore, emphasizes actions, freedom and decision as fundamental, and holds that the only way to rise above the essentially absurd condition of humanity (which is characterized by suffering and inevitable death) is by exercising our personal freedom and choice (a complete rejection of determinism. It asserts that people actually make decisions based on what has meaning to them, rather than what is rational. The important factor for existentialists is the freedom of choice to believe or not to believe.

Teachers must allow students freedom of choice and provide them with experiences that will help them find the meaning of their lives. Every individual first exists and then what his or her existence means to him or her. If students have individual freedom, ask their own questions and draw their own conclusion they will be able to find themselves as well as find out the meaning of their existence. They will have freedom to create what they desire. As a teacher, the students’ needs are extremely important. A way the teacher can best meet their needs is by offering student-teacher conferences inside or outside of class time. The discussion can be anything that is on their mind. It is important that a student knows that they can talk to their teacher. They should be comfortable around their teacher.

Behaviorism

Behaviourism can also be taught of as a form of classroom management. Behaviourists believe human beings are shaped entirely by their external environment (Dewey, 2018). If you alter a person’s environment, you will alter his or her thoughts, feelings and behaviours. The system’s-based rewards and punishments. Behaviourists believe that if teachers provide positive reinforcements or rewards, whenever students perform a desired behavior, they will learn to perform the behavior on their own, the same concept applies to punishments. Behaviourist think that people act in response to internally or externally generated physical stimuli. They basically consider human nature to be the product of one’s environment. An example of behaviourism is when teacher reward their class or certain students with a party or special treats at the end of the week for good behavior throughout the week. The same concept is used with punishments. The teacher can take away certain privileges if the students misbehave.

Behaviourism teaching methods have proven most successful in areas where there is a ‘correct’ response or easily memorized material. Behaviourist teaching methods tend to rely on so-called ‘skill and drill’ exercise to provide the consistent repetition necessary for effective enforcement of response patterns. Other methods include question (stimulus) and answer (response) framework in which questions are of gradually increasing difficulty, guided practice and regular reviews of material. Behaviourist methods also typically heavily depend on the use of positive reinforcement such as verbal praise, good grades and prizes. Behaviourists assess the degree of learning using methods that measure observable behavior such as exam performance, behaviourist teaching methods have proven most successful in areas where there is a ‘correct’ response or easily memorized material. For example, while behaviourists methods have proven to be successful in teaching structured material such as facts and formulae, scientific concepts, and foreign language vocabulary, their efficacy in teaching comprehension, composition and analytical abilities is questionable.

It’s easy to see how operant conditioning can be used for classroom management. There are many behaviours that need to be shaped (an operant term) in order to have an orderly classroom. There are indeed some classroom behaviours that

need to be shaped in order to enhance learning. For example, students could receive negative punishment for having their phones out. This might mean that they do not receive their daily attendance points. Research indicates that cell phones pull attention (Dewey, 2018).

1. So, we can use operant conditioning to increase attention and learning. However, this type of behavioural management is not the main take away here, instead, we should talk about the increasing use of good study strategies. You have seen unfortunately for many reasons, students do not readily change their study strategies, even when shown evidence that the new strategies are better.
2. In order to encourage the use of good study strategies, students need to see the direct consequence of using them. One way to do this is to give them practice using their own strategy and then require them to study some small bit of material using the new strategy you are teaching. The immediate and direct feedback that shows a higher grade is a positive reinforcement. The teacher can also provide positive reinforcement in class. He can use praise or extra credit for students who demonstrate that they are using the new strategies to try and shape their behavior. One key is that the consequence should come fairly quickly after the behavior, which is what makes this such a challenge.

Conservatism- as a teacher-centered philosophy

Conservatism can be defined as traditional, respecting ‘the old ways. A conservative education preserves the traditional curriculum, occurring to transmit information to the students as a means of bringing them into an already established culture. Conservatism is a way of individualism and change and foster assimilation and acceptance into society. They believe the primary role of education is academics, custodial, therapeutic and social functions. Such functions are believed to weaken educations.

Conclusion

The different schools of philosophical teaching approaches represent the different teaching methods that should be used in our classroom. All these approaches are vital in the effective teaching and learning process. Although teaching as a concept goes beyond what each philosophical school of thoughts says it is. Teaching should be student centered, teacher centered and society centered; since for effective teaching and of course learning to happen and for the right things to be taught to the learner for the learner to become useful to himself and the society, the teacher, learner and the society must be involved in the teaching process. Therefore, the school curriculum should be revisited from time to time for necessary adjustments. Different methods of teaching should be applied in the classrooms since each student may have different levels of absorbing or understanding what is being taught; while some students learn faster than others. It is also important to note that all learners are achievers, although some may achieve slower than others, therefore the teacher has to be patient and sometimes enduring with the slow achievers. All hands must be on deck; all stake holders in education should always be at the top of their game, meeting when necessary to find out ways to take the education sector to the next level.

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Recommendations

1. Teaching should be student, teacher and even society centered for effective teaching and learning experience.
2. The school curriculum should be revisited to capture the above (number 1).
3. Different methods should be applied in the teaching process, so as to reach each students at their different levels of ability and absorption of information.
4. All stakeholders in education should from time to time come together to discuss successes and progress made so far, adjustments where necessary and adequate funding for the education section.
5. Teachers should be patient and sometimes enduring with the slow achievers or learners in class. This is why they need to apply different teaching methods during lesson to reach all.

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